

A STUDY ON EMOTIONAL BRANDING ON CONSUMERS PERCEPTION: A NEURO-MARKETING APPROACH

Sujaya H^{*1}, Kavyashree K^{*2}, Meghana Salins^{*3}

^{*1,2}Assistant Professor, Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

^{*3}Research Scholar, Institute Of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose is to identify the rationale behind this approach is rooted in psychology, tapping into emotional triggers that affect memory retention and decision-making processes.

Design: The study includes the secondary data, with related literatures. This literature highlights various issues pertaining to the emotional branding on consumers perception in Neuro-marketing approach and the data is obtained from various case studies, reviews of literature, journals and internet sources.

Findings: Neuro-marketing research continues to uncover fascinating insights into consumer behaviour by examining brain responses to marketing stimuli.

Originality Value: Understanding the neural mechanisms behind emotional marketing is imperative for marketers striving to craft effective campaign. Moreover, in this competitive landscape, businesses are constantly seeking novel, efficient methods to analyse and predict customer actions.

Paper type: Case Study

Keywords: Emotional Branding, Consumer, Perception, Neuro-Marketing, SWOT Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Neuro-marketing is the new technique adopted using brain research has gained significance in the marketing world (Deb, A. & Academy, N. (2021). [1]).

The business searching for numerous innovative and complex processes involved in deciphering consumer minds provide innovative avenues for advertising. In today's fiercely competitive landscape, businesses are constantly seeking novel, efficient methods to analyse and predict customer actions (Cardoso, L. et al. (2022). [2]).

Furthermore, Researchers recognized the potential of integrating neuro-marketing techniques into traditional marketing research to enhance advertising strategies. Ever since Edward Bernays pioneered research in understanding the power of emotion in shaping consumer perceptions and behaviours, emotional appeals in advertising have held a prominent place (Morin, C. (2011). [3]).

Advertisers have leveraged a wide range of emotions—from fear to empathy to humour—for decades. The rationale behind this approach is rooted in psychology, tapping into emotional triggers that affect memory retention and decision-making processes. Therefore, understanding the neural mechanisms behind emotional marketing is imperative for marketers striving to craft effective campaign (Madan, M. (2016). [4]).

Neuro-marketing introduces cutting-edge techniques that enable direct exploration of the mind without relying on demanding cognitive or conscious engagement (Nyoni, T. & Bonga, W. G. (2017). [5]).

Recent advancements in neuroscience allow for the recording and analysis of even subtle neural activity, leading to paradigm shifts across various domains such as economics, computing, finance, and medicine (Cuesta, U. et al. (2018). [6]).

Prior to the emergence of neuro-marketing, there was minimal utilization of this technology to enhance understanding of customers and refine marketing strategies. Neuro-marketers decode the subconscious reactions and neural processes underlying consumer response (Keller, K. L. (1993). [7]).

By understanding how the brain responds to various marketing strategies, businesses can tailor their messaging, product design, and overall brand experience to better resonate with consumers on a deeper, subconscious level, ultimately driving more effective marketing campaigns and fostering stronger brand connections (Balconi, M. et al. (2014). [8]).

II. RELATED RESEARCH WORK

Table 1: Analysing the Emotional Branding on Consumers Perception: A Neuro-Marketing Approach

S. NO	Focus/Area	Contribution	References
1.	Focus on consumer brain works in advertising and brands.	Neuro-marketing enables the marketers to create advertising campaign more effectively with innovative product design and pricing strategies.	Plassmann, et al., (2010). [9]
2.	Consumer neuro-science strategy.	Neuro-marketing leads to paradigm shifts across various domains such as economics, computing, finance, and medicine.	Sebastian, V. (2014). [10]
3.	The emotional response of consumers in neuro-marketing and cognitive process.	It introduces cutting-edge techniques that enable direct exploration of the mind without relying on demanding cognitive or conscious engagement.	Yilmaz, B.S. et al., (2014).[11]
4.	Influencing the discrimination channels by using EEG with like/dislike analysis.	This type of approaches tailors the message and offering to go too deeper level with target audiences.	Hsu, Y. T. (2018). [12]
5.	Neuro-marketing and its ethics.	It resonates with consumers on a deeper, more intuitive level. By leveraging neuro-scientific insights, marketers can create experiences that captivate and engage consumers while fostering trust and loyalty.	Sebastian, V. A (2014). [13]
6.	The Analytical approach to neuro-marketing as a business strategy.	Researchers recognized the potential of integrating neuro-marketing techniques into traditional marketing research to enhance advertising strategies	Campero, A.A., & J.V. Hernandez. (2013).[14]
7.	Neuro- marketing agenda for future research	The future of neuro-marketing research promises to unlock new frontiers in understanding and influencing consumer behaviour.	Lee, N. (2007). [15]
8.	The professional and practical challenges of neuro-marketing.	The consumers on a deeper, subconscious level, ultimately driving more effective marketing campaigns and fostering stronger brand connections.	Carl Erik Fisher, (2010). [16]

III. METHODOLOGY

The study includes the secondary data, with related literatures. This literature highlights various issues pertaining to emotional branding on consumers perception: A Neuro-Marketing approach and the data is obtained from various case studies, reviews of literature, journals and internet sources.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To study the emotional branding on consumers perception.
2. To understand the Neuro-Marketing approach of companies.

3. To examine the existing studies on consumers' neurological reactions.
4. To study the Neuro-Marketing approach through SWOT analysis.

V. THE EMOTIONAL BRANDING ON CONSUMERS PERCEPTION

Emotions are the key drivers behind individual decisions, it plays a crucial role in shaping our unconscious and conscious thought about our willingness to buy. So companies differentiate themselves by adopting strategy of emotion marketing. Moreover, emotional branding shapes consumers' perceptions by tapping into their feelings and values, creating meaningful connections between the brand and its audience. By evoking emotions like trust or joy the emotional branding influences consumer decisions and fosters long-lasting brand loyalty (Sharma, K. et al. (2022). [17].

Emotional branding profoundly impacts consumers' perceptions by forging deep emotional connections between brands and their audience. By consumers' emotions such as trust, joy, or nostalgia, emotional branding influences consumer decisions and cultivates enduring brand loyalty. This approach transcends mere product features, resonating with consumers on a personal level and shaping their overall perception of the brand, ultimately driving preference (Hubert, M., & Kenning, P. (2008). [18]). Emotional branding holds immense power in shaping consumers' perceptions by fostering meaningful connections between brands and individuals. By strategically recall emotions such as happiness, trust, or belonging, emotional branding transcends product attributes, resonating with consumers on a profound level (Heather, C. L. et al. (2005). [19]. Through emotive storytelling, relatable messaging, and authentic experiences, brands can cultivate strong emotional bonds with their audience, influencing purchasing decisions and building enduring brand loyalty. This approach recognizes that consumers are not solely rational beings but are deeply influenced by their emotions and experiences. By tapping into these emotional triggers, brands can differentiate themselves in competitive markets, creating memorable brand experiences that resonate with consumers long after the initial interaction (Javor, A., et al. (2013) [20]).

VI. THE NEURO-MARKETING APPROACH OF COMPANIES

The revolutionized principles of companies with integration of neuro-marketing has identified the consumer behaviour for shaping the strategy. By delving the process of decision making through subconscious way neuro-marketing enables the marketers to create advertising campaign more effectively with innovative product design and pricing strategies (Kable, J. W., & Glimcher, P. W. (2009). [21]. Further, Company gains insight of customers' emotions, taste and preferences by functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and also electroencephalography (EEG). This type of approaches tailors the message and offering to go too deeper level with target audiences. However, the competitive edge provided by neuro-marketing offers a scientific base for decision making in the domain of branding and customer experience. Apparently, the understanding of the cognitive biases and heuristic play a major role in purchase decision (Liu, G., & Ko, W. (2010). [22]).

Overall, neuro-marketing approach empowers the companies for crafting the compelling narratives, to build a stronger bond with customers, and finally enhance their bottom line. In contrast, neurological tests reach a very rigorous degree of actionable results such as differences in the brain of man and women and children compared to adults. Also studies show neuro scientific methods provide insight on neuro-imaging, brain areas, subconscious and without conscious effort of participation. Study also highlight on EEG uses sensors pick up electrical signals due to brain waves activation which measures the signals when a stimulus is presented to a subject (Loss, J. et al. (2014). [23]).

VII. CONSUMERS' NEUROLOGICAL REACTIONS

The neurological reactions of consumers' play a significant role in shaping the overall perceptions and purchase decisions. Research has proved that consumer behaviour is a driving force for subconscious processes where emotions embrace long term effect. The role of advertisements or product displays are the marketing stimuli's their brain undergo drastic series neurological reactions influencing subsequent actions (Hanna, R., et al. (2011). [24]). From a broader prospective studies delve on positive emotions, such as excitement and pleasure activate reward centre of brain leading to higher level satisfaction associated with products. But conversely, negative emotion mat trigger avoidance behaviour with diminishing perceived value. So company with

reverberate understand the emotional responses and craft marketing messages that resonate with deeper and more visceral level towards target audience (Hare, T. A., et al. (2010). [25].

Digging inside consumer cognitive process of neurological reaction show the impact on attention, memory and also decision making. More surprisingly stimuli capture the attention of consumers' with increasing likelihood that they remember the brand associated with. Studies have proved that neuro-scientific methods associated with consumers rely on intuitive judgments and heuristics, other than deliberate reasoning, during decision making. The succinct picture of the leveraging insights of neurosciences show that companies need to design strategies that align the cognitive biases of customers' ultimately leading to greater conversion rate (Davidson, R. J. (2004). [26]).

VIII. SWOC ANALYSIS

Table 2: SWOT analysis on analysing the Emotional Branding on Consumers Perception (Sujaya, H. et al. (2019), Mendon, S. et al (2018), Mendon, S. et al. (2019), Salins, M. et al. (2019). [27-30]).

Constructs	Features
Strengths of the emotional branding on consumers perception in neuro marketing approach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ By evoking emotions like trust or joy the emotional branding influences consumer decisions and fosters long-lasting brand loyalty. ➤ Neuro-marketing approach empowers the companies for crafting the compelling narratives, to build a stronger bond with customers.
Weakness of the emotional branding on consumers perception in neuro marketing approach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Neurological tests reach a very rigorous degree of actionable results. Emotion mat trigger avoidance behaviour with diminishing perceived value.
Opportunity of the emotional branding on consumers perception in neuro marketing approach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Company with reverberate understand the emotional responses and craft marketing messages that resonate with deeper and more
Threats of the emotional branding on consumers perception in neuro marketing approach.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The brain undergo drastic series neurological reactions influencing subsequent actions.

IX. FINDINGS

Neuro-marketing research continues to uncover fascinating insights into consumer behaviour by examining brain responses to marketing stimuli. Recent studies have revealed that emotional engagement plays a crucial role in consumer decision-making, often overriding rational considerations. Neuroimaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and electroencephalography (EEG) have shown that certain features, such as vivid imagery, storytelling, and personal relevance, activate areas of the brain associated with emotion and memory, leading to increased attention and brand recall.

X. SUGGESTIONS

Neuro-marketing research presents a rich field for exploration, offering numerous avenues for investigation. One promising direction is the examination of cross-cultural differences in neural responses to marketing stimuli, providing valuable insights into how cultural factors shape consumer behaviour at a subconscious level. Another area ripe for study is the application of neuromarketing techniques in the context of emerging technologies such as virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), which have the potential to profoundly impact consumer experiences and perceptions. Additionally, exploring the neural mechanisms underlying consumer trust and brand loyalty could offer valuable insights into building stronger, more enduring customer relationships.

XI. CONCLUSION

Neuro-marketing research offers a compelling lens through which to understand and influence consumer behaviour. Through innovative techniques such as neuroimaging and psychophysiological measurements, this field has provided valuable insights into the subconscious processes that drive consumer decision-making. From the importance of emotional engagement to the influence of cultural factors and emerging technologies, the findings underscore the complexity and dynamism of consumer behaviour. Moving forward, continued exploration of neuro-marketing holds great promise for informing the development of more effective marketing strategies that resonate with consumers on a deeper, more intuitive level. By leveraging neuro-scientific insights, marketers can create experiences that captivate and engage consumers while fostering trust and loyalty. However, it is essential to recognize the ethical considerations inherent in neuro-marketing research and practice, ensuring that insights are used responsibly and with respect for consumer well-being.

XII. REFERENCES

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